

COMBINATION OF GLOMERULONEPHRITIS AND NEPHROTIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN: CLINICAL AND LABORATORY ANALYSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18622124>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2026

Accepted: 11th February 2026

Online: 12th February 2026

KEYWORDS

To identify and evaluate the specific features of clinical signs and laboratory parameters in the combined course of glomerulonephritis and nephrotic syndrome in children

ABSTRACT

Although glomerulonephritis (GN) and nephrotic syndrome (NS) have been widely studied as separate nosological entities in pediatric nephrology, their coexistence poses complex diagnostic and treatment problems in clinical practice. This condition is characterized by a severe course of the disease, frequent relapses, and a high risk of developing chronic renal failure. Therefore, a thorough analysis of clinical and laboratory parameters in the combined manifestation of GN and NS is of great importance.

Introduction

Although glomerulonephritis (GN) and nephrotic syndrome (NS) have been widely studied as separate nosological entities in pediatric nephrology, their coexistence poses complex diagnostic and treatment problems in clinical practice. This condition is characterized by a severe course of the disease, frequent relapses, and a high risk of developing chronic renal failure. Therefore, a thorough analysis of clinical and laboratory parameters in the combined manifestation of GN and NS is of great importance.

Objectives: To identify and evaluate the specific features of clinical signs and laboratory parameters in the combined course of glomerulonephritis and nephrotic syndrome in children.

Methods

The study retrospectively analyzed the medical records of children treated in the nephrology department. Patients were evaluated based on clinical symptoms (edema, arterial hypertension, diuresis disorders), general urinalysis, biochemical blood tests (total protein, albumin, cholesterol, creatinine, urea) and immunological parameters.

Results and Discussion

According to the results of the analysis, in children with concomitant GN and NS, general edema syndrome, high proteinuria, hypoproteinemia, and hyperlipidemia were identified as the leading clinical and laboratory signs. Arterial hypertension and hematuria were more common in cases with a predominance of GN. A decrease in renal function was observed in some patients at an early stage, which indicates a severe course of the disease.

Conclusion

The concomitant course of glomerulonephritis and nephrotic syndrome is a clinically more severe and complex form of the disease in children. A comprehensive assessment of clinical and laboratory indicators is important for early diagnosis, selection of individual treatment tactics, and prevention of complications.

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